

Effect of fungicides on B1 incidence and rice yield, Punjab, Pakistan.^a

Fungicide	Formulation (g/litre water)	One spray			Two sprays			Three sprays		
		% B1 incidence	Yield (t/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio ^b	% B1 incidence	Yield (t/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio	% B1 incidence	Yield (t/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Phthalide 30 WP	1.5	33 a	1.4 a	3.0:1	23 b	2.0 b	10.0:1	14 a	2.4 bc	10.4:1
Phthalide 30 WP	2.5	29 a	1.4 a	3.5:1	8 a	2.5 a	11.5:1	4 a	3.2 a	12.1:1
Kasugamycin 2 WP	1.5	48 b	1.3 a	1.2:1	30 b	1.9 b	8.4:1	23 b	2.2 c	8.7:1
Kasugamycin 2 WP	2.5	46 b	1.4 a	2.1:1	16 ab	2.1 ab	8.4:1	10 a	2.9 ab	9.8:1
Check	—	59 c	1.2 a	—	68 c	1.2 c	—	65 c	1.2 d	—
Cd ₁	—	11	0.2	—	14	0.4	—	9	0.6	—

^a Av of 4 trials. In a column numbers followed by common letters are statistically identical at 95% level of confidence. ^b Benefit-cost ratios were calculated by dividing extra benefits attained from the enhanced yield by the extra costs incurred for each treatment. The costs included fungicide price at \$10/kg, application costs (\$2.25/spray). Benefits included the price of enhanced yield over that of the check @ \$6/40 kg paddy.

farmers' fields in Sheikhpura District.

Basmati 370 was transplanted in 25.5-m² plots the first week of August. One, 2, or 3 sprays of 250 litres fungicide/ha were applied in 3 replications. Phthalide 30 WP and kasugamycin 2 WP at 1.5 and 2.5 g/litre water were compared with the check. A single fungicide spray was applied 60 d after transplanting

(DT). In trials with 2 or 3 applications, the first application was at 45 DT, with succeeding applications at 15-d intervals.

Leaf B1 incidence was recorded 10 d after the last spray by counting and calculating percentages of leaves with B1 lesions from five randomly chosen plants from each plot. Internodal and nodal B1 incidence was recorded at crop

maturity from 2 randomly selected 1-m quadrats in each plot.

All treatments significantly reduced B1 incidence (see table). One spray did not significantly increase yield over that of the check, but two and three sprays did. Two and three applications had higher benefit-cost ratio than one application. *J*

Chemical control of sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk. is spreading in major rice growing areas in Thailand. There are few resistant varieties; therefore chemical controls are needed. In 1984, we tested 13 fungicides for ShB control at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station. Susceptible RD7 was planted in 1.5 × 3-m plots in a randomized complete block design. Plants were inoculated at tillering by inserting a pack of mycelia grown on sterilized rice grain. Fungicides were sprayed 3 and 10 d later. Disease intensity was recorded 3 wk after inoculation by measuring lesion length on leaf sheaths of each tiller.

All fungicides significantly reduced disease intensity. Pencycuron 25% WP, Jinguinmycin 5% liquid, validamycin 3% liquid, carbendazim 60% WP, and mepronil 75% WP, were most effective (see table). *J*

Effectiveness of certain chemicals against ShB of rice.

Fungicide	Application rate (g ai/ha)	Lesion length (cm)
Pencycuron 25% WP	315	29.2 a
Jinguinmycin 5% liquid	50	29.6 a
Validamycin 3% liquid	45	29.8 a
Carbendazim 60% WP	600	32.5 a
Mepronil 75% WP	1225	33.7 a
Iprodione 50% WP	500	39.5 b
Propiconazole 25% EC	250	41.3 b
Thiophanate-methyl 50% ULV	500	44.1 bc
Thiabendazol 90% WP	900	48.6 cd
Polyoxin + IBP 42% WP	630	49.7 d
Polyoxin Z 2.2% WP	33	56.9 e
Polyoxin D 2% WP	30	60.0 ef
Furmecycloz 40% WP	600	63.7 f
Control	0	73.5 g

CV = 7.0%

Sclerotia distribution of *Rhizoctonia solani* and its relation to sheath blight (ShB) in Arkansas rice fields

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We studied the relationship between inoculum density and ShB development and the factors that influence sclerotia distribution and density in rice fields.

Rice production fields with a history of severe ShB incidence were selected for sclerotia distribution studies. One-litre soil samples were taken 2-3 wk after rice emerged, but before permanent flooding, at 114-cm intervals and 1.5-cm depth.

Samples were air-dried in open pots and suspended in 2.5 litres of water for 5 min. The supernatant was washed through a 4-mm mesh sieve over 0.50-mm mesh sieve. The process was repeated with the material left in the pot, but with only 3 min suspension.